

Agroforestry in CAP Strategic Plans - Finland

EURAF Policy Briefing 34 (v1 31.1.25) 10.5281/zenodo.14777568

Authors: Michael den Herder (European Forest Institute, Finnish Agroforestry Network), Joshua Finch (Novia University of Applied Sciences, Finnish Agroforestry Network), Iiris Mattila (Kilpiä Farm, Finnish Agroforestry Network), Tanja Kähkönen (European Forest Institute, Finnish Agroforestry Network), Gerry Lawson (EURAF)

Finnish version [HERE](#).

EURAF is an NGO, based in Montpellier and Brussels (Transparency Register ID of [913270437706-82](#)). It aims "to promote the adoption of agroforestry practices across Europe by supporting efforts to develop awareness, education, research, policy making and investments which foster the use of trees on farms". It has a network of 31 affiliated entities in 23 countries.

1 Definition of Agroforestry

Section 4.1.2.1 of the first Finnish [CAP Strategic Plan](#) (CSP version 1.1) defined agroforestry as: *A windbreak planted as a narrow strip of trees and/or shrubs can be planted following the edge of a parcel and will be part of the eligible area for basic payments. Section 4.1.8 clarifies that "If more than 50% of the agricultural area of a plot is under grasses or other herbaceous forage crops, the permanent grassland parcel **may contain trees other than seedlings** of deciduous trees suitable for grazing and feeding to farm animals (see point 4.1.2.4.7) up to 50 plants per hectare if they are scattered over the plot. The number of trees does not take into account trees in windbreaks in arable forestry."* This definition is unchanged in the latest [Finnish CSP](#) (version 4.2).

Photo 1. *Traditional rural landscape with natural pastures and meadows on Ahvenanmaa in the Finnish archipelago (Photo Michael den Herder).*

2 Definition of Permanent Grassland

Section 4.1.2.4 of the Finnish CSP gives the definition of "grasses and other herbaceous forage" as "... including those species of grasses and herbaceous forage plants which are traditionally found in natural pastures or in

mixtures of grass, pasture or meadow seed." However Finland also ticked the box regarding "inclusion of other species such as trees and/or shrubs which produce animal feed, **provided that grasses and other herbaceous forage remain predominant**". It is possible, however, that this extended definition applies only to specific regions or districts.

3 Good Agricultural and Environmental Conditions for biodiversity and landscape (GAEC 8)

Section 2.3 summarises choices made by all Member States for Good Agricultural and Environmental Conditions (GAEC 8). As "Landscape Features and Non Productive Areas" Finland recognised only "fallow land". Another exemption is that GAEC 8 targets only apply in Finland's two southernmost regions [14] - since all other NUTS3 regions in Finland have more than 50% forest cover. Finland of course is, in relative terms, the most forested country in Europe (74%).

4 Eco-schemes (Art 31):

There are only [four eco-schemes](#) in Finland and none specifically mentions agroforestry (Table 1). Eco-scheme 02 applies to natural pastures and meadows. When trees and shrubs are present, these can be considered as a type of silvopastoral system.

Table 1 Article 31 Eco-schemes in Finland

Eco-scheme	Financial %	UAA %
01 – Winter Vegetation Cover	81.40	61.67
02 – Natural Grasslands	6.98	3.96
03 – Green manure root crops	2.91	1.32
04 – Biodiversity crops	8.72	1.10

Table 2 Article 70 Agri Environment Climate Measures implemented in the Finnish CSP 2023-2028

Code	Measure
EDV 01	Field plan for livestock
EDV 02	Sick, treatment and calving boxes for livestock
EDV 03	Promoting the conditions under which fish are kept
EDV 04	Promotion of conditions under which male bovine animals are kept
EDV 05	Welfare plan for sheep and goats
EDV 06	Promotion of conditions under which sheep and goats are kept
EKO	Organic production
MILJ 01	Farm-wide environmental commitment
MILJ 02	Cultivation of soil-improving and remediation plants
MILJ 03	Cultivation of catch crops
MILJ 04	Alternative plant protection methods in horticulture
MILJ 05	Promoting the circular economy.
MILJ 06	Creation of grassed protection zones
MILJ 07	Natural pasture management
MILJ 08	Targeted management measures on natural pastures
MILJ 09	Breeding of indigenous breeds
ILJ 10	Cultivation of migratory plants for bees
EHK 01	Automotive hygiene programme
EHK 02	Calving, grooming and farrowing pens for cattle
EHK 03	Improving conditions for calves
HK 04	Improving conditions for male cattle
EHK 05	Cattle grazing
K 06	Outdoor exercise for cattle
EHK 07	Pig welfare plan
EHK 08	Free boring
EHK 09	Improved farrowing conditions

EHK 10	Improving conditions for sows/sows
EHK 11	Improving conditions for weaned piglets
EHK 12	Improving conditions for meat pigs
EHK 13	Sheep and goat welfare plan
EHK 14	Improving conditions for sheep and goats
EHK 15	Grazing of sheep and goats
EHK 16	Poultry welfare plan
HK 17	Improving conditions for poultry
Organic	Commitment to organic production
Environment 01	Farm-specific measure
Environment 02	Land improvement and renovation crops
Environment 03	Forage plants
Environment 04	Promoting the circular economy
Environment 05	Protection zones
Environment 06	Peatland grassland
Environment 07	Drainage water management
Environment 08	Alternative plant protection for horticultural crops
Environment 09	Bird fields
Environment 10	Management of agricultural nature and landscape
Environment 11	Wetland management
Environment 12	Breeding indigenous breeds
Environment 13	Native plant maintenance
Environment 14	Conservation of the genetic heritage of indigenous breeds
Environment 15	Native plant collections

5 Pillar II schemes:

In contrast to the small number of eco-schemes there are a huge number of AECM and INVESTMENT Pillar II measures in Finland. Some of these may be suitable for funding agroforestry or tree planting, but no specific mention is made of this.

5.1 Agri-environmental and Climate Measures (AECM)

There are 50 AECM Measures in Finland: a large number of which appear to be related to animal welfare (Table 2). Again, there could be some opportunity for agroforestry wood pastures in "[nature pasture management](#)" and "[targeted management measures on natural pastures](#)", but existing documentation for these schemes does not make a specific mention on the number of trees. Finnish expenditure on forestry is does not go through the Common Agricultural Policy, but is supported under the "Temporary Forestry Incentive Scheme" ([link](#)) from national budgets ([link](#)), under the terms of the "Agricultural Block Exemption Regulation (EURAF [Policy Briefing #19](#))". This has a chapter on agroforestry, but it appears not to be used in Finland

5.2 Investment Measures

There are 19 Investment measures in Finland, but only "non-productive investments to promote biodiversity, or for the sustainable management of natural resources" appears to have potential to fund the establishment of agroforestry or "landscape features" (Table 3). Forestry investments in Finland are funded outside of Common Agricultural Policy funds.

Table 3 Investment measures implemented in the Finnish CSP (2023-2028)

Code	Measure
IP diversity	Non-productive investments to promote biodiversity
IP nat.res.	Non-productive investments for the sustainable management of natural resources
irrigation	Investments in irrigation and land drainage
energy agriculture	Energy investments for farms
NV förädl föret	Investing in the processing and salvaging of animal products outside the EU
jordbr	Investing in competitiveness & modernisation of farms
wetland	Wetland investment
Broadband	Rural Broadband Investment
Agriculture 01	Development of the competitiveness and modernisation of agricultural holdings
Agriculture 02	Energy investments in agricultural holdings
Agriculture 03	Investments in farms to promote environmental condition and sustainable production
Agriculture 04	Investments to improve animal welfare and biosecurity
General Benefit 01	Investments in climate change mitigation and adaptation climate change
Public Benefit 02	Public Benefit Investments in the Sustainable Management of Natural Resources
General Benefit 03	Public Benefit Investments for Biodiversity
General Benefit 04	Investment in rural environment development
company 01	Investments in renewable energy and biofuels
enterprise 02	Investments in processing and marketing of agricultural and natural products
enterprise 03	Investment in micro and small enterprises and multisectoral agricultural holdings

6 Indicators (R.17, O.16):

No mention is made of Indicator R.17 (area of afforestation, regeneration and agroforestation) or O.16 (area of afforestation or agroforestation which is under annual maintenance agreements).

7 Commission observation letter

The Commission's [observation letter](#) mentions AF three times. These questions may not have been responded to in the final CSP - e.g. mention of "protected trees" (93) . The Finnish CSP is unique amongst Member States in that NO landscape features have been mentioned as contributing to GAEC 8, nor are any marked for protection in the Finnish Land Parcel Identification System..

- 46. Considering the needs identified, Finland is invited to reinforce the interventions with direct effect on nutrient surplus (e.g. organic farming, **agroforestry**) and include, if necessary, additional interventions.
- 80. Section 4.1.2.1: provide clearer information on the elements of **agroforestry** based e.g. on type of trees, their size, number, distribution in relation to pedo-climatic conditions or management practices.
- 93. Finland is invited to explain in relation to the biodiversity objective why there is a maximum share of 10% of area devoted to biodiversity... . Finland is also invited to explain what are the “protected trees” retained under this GAEC standard and in particular the link with the definition of agricultural area (e.g. “arable land does not in principle include trees **other than approved landscape features or in the case of agroforestry**”), and apply the ban on cutting trees during the bird breeding and rearing season to all trees.

Photo 2. Restoring soil health in a pilot EU-funded successional silvoarable system in Kirkkonummi, a town in southern Finland (Photo by Johan Ljungqvist, Multifoto AB/Oy. June 14, 2024)

8 Inclusion of agroforestry in the Finnish Land Parcel Identification System (LPIS)

The Finnish LPIS uses geographic information system (GIS) technologies, satellite imagery, and aerial photographs to accurately map agricultural parcels across the country. Finnish farmers submit information about their land parcels, which is cross-verified with the LPIS database to determine eligibility for subsidies.

The Finnish Land Parcel Identification System is publicly available (there is a [public viewer](#) and a [download site](#)). The public 2023 version contains information on land cover (arable land, grassland or permanent crops), area under organic farming, area under Natura 2000, areas important for drinking water, woody landscape features, and cropping areas. The system also contains information on CAP eligibility, but this is not publicly available. The system does not contain complete information on agroforestry but the following categories (for year 2023) which can be considered as agroforestry are included in the system:

Environmental agreements, tree or other surface (crop code: 9813 – in Finnish: *Ympäristösopimusala, puustoinen tai muu ala*)

Environmental agreements promote the restoration and preservation of the diversity of agricultural nature and landscape. Management measures must be used to preserve or promote valuable nature or landscape values in the contract area by managing areas or sites that are important for the preservation and reproduction of plant and animal species as well as the agricultural landscape. The agreement requires annual grazing or maintenance of the contract area by mowing and removing mowing residues. More information [here](#).

If there are more than 50 trees per hectare, the parcel is reported under *Environmental agreement with trees or other surface*. If there are less than 50 trees per hectare, the parcel is reported under *Environmental agreements for areas with permanent grass*.

Area under organic certification (non-agricultural land) (crop code: 9651 – *in Finnish*: Muu luomuvalvonnalla (ei maatalousmaata)

If you graze organic animals elsewhere than on agricultural land, for example forest land, you can report this field under *Area under organic certification (non-agricultural land)*. The land use type of the parcel must be Forest land or Other area. More information [here](#).

Permanent grass and environmental agreements for areas with permanent grass

In addition, some other LPIS crop/land use categories may contain agroforestry, for instance, permanent grassland. However, not all permanent grasslands have trees and therefore not all permanent grasslands are agroforestry. Therefore, in order to assess tree presence on permanent grassland, additional assessments would be needed, for instance through remote sensing.

Permanent grass is an area that is used to grow hay or other grass fodder plants that have been in the same place for more than 5 years, either by natural growth or by sowing. The land use type of permanent grass can be a field or natural pasture and meadow.

A maximum of 50 trees per hectare may grow scattered on permanent grass. Single- or multi-stemmed trees and woody shrubs with a height of at least four metres are considered trees. Junipers of any size are also considered trees. Trees in windbreak plantings are not taken into account in the number of trees. Deciduous shrubs and saplings of deciduous trees suitable for feeding farm animals may grow in the area if they cover less than half of the surface area of the eligible parcel.

More than half (50%) of the surface area of the parcel must have hay and grass fodder plants. The requirement also applies to those parcels of permanent grass that have trees or deciduous shrubs or both. More information [here](#).

Some permanent grassland LPIS categories have a high likelihood of tree presence, these are for instance: natural pastures and meadows (crop code 6300 - *Luonnonlaidun ja -niitty*; crop code 6308 – *Luonnonlaidun sopimusala (Ahvenanmaa)*), buffer strips (crop code 9820 - *Suojakaista*), buffer zones (crop code 9809 - *Suojavyöhyke*), green fallow (grass and meadow) (crop code 9412 - *Viherkesanto (nurmi ja niitty)*), Environmental agreement area, permanent grass (crop code 9805 - *Ympäristösopimusala, pysyvä nurmi*).

Windbreaks

Windbreaks are allowed without a restriction on the number of trees per hectare. The surface area of the windbreak can be considered as part of the basic parcel. Windbreak planting refers to a row of trees or bushes planted on the edge of a parcel. The planting area must follow the edge of the parcel and can be no more than 2 metres wide. If the planting is located in the middle of the basic parcel, it must be divided.

Planting cannot be done on the edge of the basic parcel bordering forest. Along water courses, the windbreak does not replace the buffer strip. Shrubs or trees that have naturally formed on the edge of a parcel are not accepted as windbreaks.

9 Tree cover density on agricultural land

This analysis is based on den Herder et al ([2020](#)), but updated using 2018 data for Copernicus Tree Cover Density at 100m resolution ([\[Copernicus\] 2020](#)), superimposed on Corine data ([Feranec et al. 2016](#)) for four categories of agricultural land (Table 4). The analysis is focused on areas with greatest potential for tree planting, and therefore excluded the following agricultural categories: 121 (agricultural buildings), 242 (agriculture with significant areas of natural vegetation), 221 (vineyards), 222 (fruit trees and berry plantations), , 241 (annual crops associated with

permanent crops), 242 (complex cultivation patterns). A separate analysis was made with and without Natura 2000 areas, but the data shown here includes Natura 2000.

Table 4. Area (ha) in each of the Copernicus tree crown cover classes and Corine agricultural land categories, including Natura 2000

Corine land cover code	0%	<= 1%	<= 2%	<= 5%	<= 10%	<= 100
211- arable	996,725	1,070,484	1,118,911	1,217,592	1,323,959	1,675,839
231 - grassland	2,372	2,496	2,584	2,760	2,946	3,649
<i>Sum</i>	<i>999,097</i>	<i>1,072,980</i>	<i>1,121,495</i>	<i>1,220,352</i>	<i>1,326,905</i>	<i>1,679,488</i>
%	59.5%	63.9%	66.8%	72.7%	79.0%	100.0%

Notes: **211** includes cereals, legumes, fodder crops, root crops and fallow land. Includes flowers and fruit trees (nursery cultivation) and vegetables, whether open field, under plastic or glass (includes market gardening). Includes aromatic, medicinal and culinary plants. Does not include permanent pastures. **231** includes dense grass cover, of floral composition, dominated by graminacea, not under a rotation system. Mainly for grazing, but the fodder may be harvested mechanically. See text for the classes which are excluded.

The Finnish Zero-Tree-Index is shown in red as 59.5%. This is the fifth lowest in the EU-27 and compares with a median per Member State of 70.1%.

Figure 1: Tree cover density in Finland on agricultural land, excluding Natura 2000 areas using Copernicus data for 2018. Deep red colours indicate crown covers below 0.05% in each 100m pixel

10 SWOT Analysis

10.1. Strengths

- Strong trust in institutions, organisations
- Finns have a strong tradition of working together through networks and associations, which can help the spread of agroforestry knowledge sharing
- Changing attitudes of citizens and consumers towards valuing positive environmental outcomes
- Farms are often family farms, which increases the possibilities of long-term thinking
- Agroforestry may strengthen community by landscape, ecosystems services, collaboration between farms, local entrepreneurship, local food
- Forestry culture: farmers, citizens, government- they all live close to trees

10.2 Weaknesses

- No inclusion of agroforestry in CAP eco-schemes (Article 31), Investment measures (Article 73), or agri-environment-climate measures (Article 70).
- No recognition of Landscape Features, including trees outside forests, in Finland. It is the only country in Europe where this is the case.
- Advisory groups and individuals, as well as policy makers, are generally unfamiliar with agroforestry
- High production costs (diesel, equipment, labour)
- A lack of data from working agroforestry examples from which to develop well grounded design parameters
- Low species diversity, compared to southern Europe, reduces design choices
- The forestry sector has a long history of set ways

10.3 Opportunities

- Agroforestry supports existing policy measures around biodiversity, conservation, environmental protection, animal welfare, and nutrient policies¹
- Collaboration with established Swedish agroforestry development and networks
- Emerging interest from researchers, farmers, education institutions can be leveraged for policy and practical developments
- Value chains and consumer preferences align well with the products, experiences, and stories from agroforestry
- A national LULUCF target of 17.754 MtCO₂eq by 2030, whereas its 2021 net sequestration is close to zero ([link](#)).
- No mention of trees outside forests in the Finnish National Energy and Climate Plan ([link](#))
- Direct to consumer marketing and cooperation (CSA) can improve profit margin
- Agroforestry can strengthen many farms' ecosystem functions
- Other farm enterprises benefit from whole systems thinking required for agroforestry
- Woody plants and grazing go well together, both in silvopasture and wooded pasture scenarios which have a strong basis in many parts of Finland
- New forms of ecological compensation may be coming: agroforestry planted now may benefit later
- Ecotourism
- New opportunities may result in greater economic activity in local areas

10.4 Threats

- Many agroforestry systems may not be established unless supported by government subsidies

¹ Suomen biodiversiteettipolitiikka: <https://ym.fi/suomen-biodiversiteettipolitiikka> ; EU Biodiversity strategy for 2030:

https://environment.ec.europa.eu/strategy/biodiversity-strategy-2030_en

- Failures of early adoption of agroforestry can reduce the reputation of the concept as a whole
- Fears of production loss
- Competition for resources to support differing visions of agriculture in light of climate change and ecological crises
- Practical threat: high loss rates to wildlife (browsing animals such as deer, voles, rabbits), control measures raise expenses

11 References

Copernicus Land Monitoring Service (2020) Tree Cover Density 2018 (raster 100 m)

<https://doi.org/10.2909/c7bf34ea-755c-4dbd-85b6-4efc5fd302a2>

den Herder, M. et al. (2020) Agroforestry in the EU Forest Strategy .EURAF Policy Briefing#2. European Agroforestry Federation. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7936685>

Feranec, J., Soukup, T., Hazeu, G., Jaffrain, G. (Eds.), 2016. European Landscape Dynamics: CORINE Land Cover Data. CRC Press, Boca Raton. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781315372860>

---	---	---